

Supplemental Material: Critical Activation Voltage for Phonon-Mediated Field-Driven Phenomena

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TRANSIENT THERMAL MODEL

To compute the classical thermal baseline (ρ_{CRC}) for bulk wire experiments, the full non-adiabatic transient energy balance was solved at every time step:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{mass}} C_p(T) \frac{dT}{dt} = & J(t)^2 \rho(T) \\ & - \frac{4}{d} \epsilon(T) \sigma_{\text{SB}} (T^4 - T_0^4) \\ & - \frac{8}{L^2} \kappa(T) (T - T_0) f_{\text{diff}}(t) \\ & - \frac{4}{d} h_{\text{conv}}(T) (T - T_0), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the four terms on the right-hand side represent Joule heating, Stefan–Boltzmann radiative losses, axial conduction to the clamps, and natural convection to ambient air, respectively. Here T is the wire temperature, $T_0 = 300$ K is ambient, $J(t)$ is the applied current density, $\rho(T)$ is the electrical resistivity, d is the wire diameter, L is the gauge length between voltage probes, $\epsilon(T)$ is the total hemispherical emissivity, σ_{SB} is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant, and $\kappa(T)$ is the thermal conductivity.

The diffusion-limited axial conduction ramp prevents the conduction loss term from exceeding its steady-state value before the thermal diffusion front has reached the wire midpoint:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\text{diff}}(t) = \min\left(1, \frac{2\alpha(T)t}{L^2}\right), \\ \alpha(T) = \frac{\kappa(T)}{\rho_{\text{mass}} C_p(T)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The natural convection coefficient was computed using the Churchill–Chu correlation for a long horizontal cylinder:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Nu} = \left[0.60 + \frac{0.387 \text{Ra}^{1/6}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{0.559}{\text{Pr}}\right)^{9/16}\right)^{8/27}} \right]^2, \\ h_{\text{conv}} = \frac{\text{Nu} k_{\text{air}}}{d}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with the Rayleigh number and film-temperature definitions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ra} = \frac{g \beta \Delta T d^3}{\nu_{\text{air}}^2} \text{Pr}, \quad \Delta T \equiv T - T_0, \\ \beta \equiv 1/T_f, \quad T_f = (T + T_0)/2. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Air properties were evaluated at the film temperature T_f :

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{\text{air}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \left(\frac{T_f}{300}\right)^{1.7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}, \\ k_{\text{air}} = 0.026 \left(\frac{T_f}{300}\right)^{0.8} \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K}), \\ \text{Pr} = 0.71. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

All material properties (ρ , C_p , κ , ϵ) were treated as temperature-dependent and interpolated from CRC Handbook tabulated data (97th ed.; Desai, Matula, White & Minges).

DERIVATION OF V_c FROM ELECTRON–PHONON COUPLING

The electron–phonon Hamiltonian

The interaction between electrons and lattice vibrations is described by coupling matrix elements whose form depends on bonding character. For polar optical phonons (ionic materials):

$$|g_{\mathbf{q}}|^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2 \hbar \omega_{\text{LO}}}{V q^2} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{\infty}} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \right), \quad (6)$$

and for deformation-potential coupling (metals and covalent materials):

$$|g_{\mathbf{q}}|^2 = \frac{\hbar q^2 D^2}{2M\omega_q}, \quad (7)$$

where D is the deformation potential and M the atomic mass.

Phonon damping and the universal ridge

The electron–phonon interaction modifies the phonon propagator through the self-energy $\Pi(q, \omega)$. The imaginary part gives the phonon linewidth:

$$\Gamma(q) = -2 \text{Im}[\Pi(q, \omega_q)]. \quad (8)$$

Ding *et al.* demonstrated that all solids follow a universal damping function [1]:

$$\Gamma(q) = \Gamma_0 \frac{q^4}{(q_0^2 - q^2)^2 + q^2 \theta^2}, \quad (9)$$

where $q_0 = a/\xi$ is set by the characteristic scatterer size ξ , $\theta = a/\ell$ by the phonon mean free path ℓ , and the prefactor connects directly to electron–phonon coupling:

$$\Gamma_0 = \alpha |g|^2 N(E_F) \xi^2, \quad (10)$$

with $\alpha \approx \pi$ a dimensionless constant and $N(E_F)$ the electronic density of states at the Fermi level.

Phonon softening at the universal ridge

The phonon eigenfrequency under damping is:

$$\Omega(q) = \Omega_0(q) \exp\left[-\frac{\Gamma(q)}{2cq_D}\right], \quad (11)$$

where $\Omega_0(q) = (2cq_D/\pi) \sin(\pi q/2q_D)$ is the undamped Debye dispersion. Maximum damping occurs at $q^*/q_D \approx 0.73$, where $d\Gamma/dq = 0$. We define the softening factor:

$$k_{\text{soft}} = \left[\frac{\Omega(q^*)}{\Omega_0(q^*)}\right]^2 = \exp\left[-\frac{\Gamma(q^*)}{cq_D}\right]. \quad (12)$$

Parameterizing in terms of a ridge parameter β :

$$k_{\text{soft}} = 1 - \beta (q^*/q_D)^2 = 1 - 0.533 \beta, \quad (13)$$

where expanding the exponential for moderate damping and substituting Γ_0 gives:

$$\beta \approx \frac{\alpha |g|^2 N(E_F) \xi^2 (0.73)^2}{cq_D \theta}. \quad (14)$$

The threshold condition and master equation

Field-activated behavior initiates when the net driving force crosses zero:

$$k_{\text{soft}} |\Delta G^\circ(T)| - nFEr = 0, \quad (15)$$

where $\Delta G^\circ(T)$ is the standard Gibbs energy for defect formation, n is the number of electrons transferred, F is Faraday’s constant, E is the applied field, and r is the onset activation coherence length. Since k_{soft} and ΔG° are material properties, the product $Er = V_c$ is invariant:

$$V_c = Er = \frac{k_{\text{soft}}}{nF} |\Delta G^\circ(T)|. \quad (16)$$

Substituting $k_{\text{soft}} = 1 - 0.533 \beta$ and defining the reduced coupling $\tilde{g}^2 \equiv \pi \hbar |g|^2 N(E_F) \xi^2 / k_B \Theta_D \theta$:

$$V_c = \frac{|\Delta G^\circ(T)|}{nF} [1 - 0.533 \tilde{g}^2]. \quad (17)$$

This master equation connects the experimentally measured critical activation voltage V_c to the fundamental electron–phonon coupling strength g .

Physical interpretation

In the weak-coupling limit ($g \rightarrow 0$, metals), $\tilde{g}^2 \rightarrow 0$ and $V_c \rightarrow |\Delta G^\circ|/nF$. For typical metallic defect energies ($|\Delta G^\circ| \approx 90\text{--}120$ kJ/mol, $n \approx 1$), this yields $V_c \approx 0.09\text{--}0.12$ V, matching the observed $V_c \approx 0.1$ V for FCC, BCC, and HCP metals.

In the strong-coupling limit (covalent materials), larger \tilde{g}^2 reduces k_{soft} but the thermodynamic barrier $|\Delta G^\circ|$ for defect formation is simultaneously large ($\sim 6\text{--}7$ eV), yielding V_c up to 2.7 V for WC.

CONNECTION TO THE UNIVERSAL PHONON RIDGE

Ding *et al.* [1] and Baggioli and Zaccone [2] showed that maximum phonon softening in all solids occurs at the boson-peak/van Hove singularity boundary at $q^*/q_D = 0.73$. This universal ridge geometry determines k_{soft} through Eq. (13). Evaluating:

$$k_{\text{soft}} = 1 - (q^*/q_D)^2 = 1 - 0.533 = 0.467. \quad (18)$$

Our empirically fitted mean $k_{\text{soft}} \approx 0.45$ for ionic oxides matches this theoretical prediction, confirming that field-driven lattice instabilities access the universal phonon damping resonance.

At the ridge, the phonon correlation length is $\xi^* = 2\pi/q^* \approx 1.4a$, where a is the lattice parameter. For $a = 5$ Å, $\xi^* \approx 7$ Å. The macroscopic coherence length r (μm scale) represents cooperative behavior across $N_{\text{cell}} = r/\xi^* \approx 14,000$ phonon wavelengths—reflecting the collective nature of the field-activated state.

COMPLETE DATASET

Table I presents the complete tabulated dataset of 73 field-activated experiments used in this study. For each experiment, the applied electric field E , onset temperature T_{onset} , fitted coherence length r , critical activation voltage $V_c = Er$, and phonon softening factor k_{soft} are listed. Source DOIs are provided in the main text reference list.

TABLE I: Complete dataset of 73 field-activated experiments across 40 materials and 17 crystal families.

#	Material	Family	E (V/cm)	T_{on} (K)	r (μm)	V_c (V)	k_{soft}
1	(La,Ta)-TiO ₂	rutile	300	1373	13.0	0.390	0.25
2	HEP	pyrochlore	150	1323	22.5	0.338	0.25
3	(Nb,Ta,Ti)N	nitride	32	1123	339.3	1.086	0.82
4	(Zr,Ce)O ₂	fluorite	250	1473	10.4	0.260	0.26
5	3YSZ	fluorite	120	1123	35.2	0.422	0.26
6	3YSZ-Al ₂ O ₃	composite	150	1573	15.5	0.233	0.26
7	3YSZ (5 MPa)	fluorite	100	1148	38.6	0.386	0.26
8	8YSZ	fluorite	100	1073	41.3	0.413	0.25
9	Al ₂ O ₃ -3YSZ	oxide comp.	150	1348	24.1	0.362	0.28
10	GDC10	fluorite	50	1373	77.8	0.389	0.25
11	Gd:Sm-Pr-CeO ₂	fluorite	50	998	85.3	0.427	0.25
12	MgAl ₂ O ₄	spinel	750	673	5.7	0.428	0.29
13	MgAl ₂ O ₄	spinel	1000	673	4.2	0.420	0.29
14	MgO-Al ₂ O ₃	corundum	1000	1533	4.0	0.400	0.30
15	NaNbO ₃	perovskite	400	1283	7.2	0.288	0.20
16	NaNbO ₃	perovskite	500	1249	5.7	0.285	0.20
17	NaNbO ₃	perovskite	600	1189	4.9	0.294	0.20
18	NaNbO ₃	perovskite	700	1135	4.3	0.301	0.20
19	Ni	FCC	2	1273	500	0.100	0.73
20	Porc. Stoneware	glass cer.	500	1173	4.1	0.205	0.21
21	Porc. Stoneware	glass cer.	450	1223	4.4	0.198	0.21
22	Porc. Stoneware	glass cer.	400	1273	4.9	0.196	0.21
23	Porc. Stoneware	glass cer.	350	1323	5.5	0.193	0.21
24	Re	HCP	100	1173	13.4	0.134	0.73
25	SDC	fluorite	120	1123	26.9	0.323	0.25
26	SiCw/3YSZ	composite	80	1273	29.9	0.239	0.26
27	SnO ₂ (AC)	rutile	80	1373	41.5	0.332	0.26
28	SrFe ₁₂ O ₁₉	ferrite	40	1123	79.9	0.320	0.27
29	SrTiFe _x O _{3-δ}	perovskite	600	1123	3.9	0.234	0.20
30	W	BCC	2	1273	500	0.100	0.73
31	WC	carbide	120	1123	227.5	2.730	0.83
32	ZrN	nitride	32	1023	321.4	1.028	0.82
33	c-ZrO ₂ (SC)	fluorite	230	588	20.1	0.462	0.26
34	α -Al ₂ O ₃	corundum	1500	1173	3.3	0.495	0.30
35	α -SiC	carbide	20	2358	158.9	0.318	0.83
36	B ₄ C	carbide	40	1473	114.3	0.457	0.83
37	B ₄ C	carbide	200	1673	21.2	0.424	0.83
38	Co ₂ MnO ₄	spinel	50	873	82.0	0.410	0.29
39	Co ₂ MnO ₄	spinel	100	773	40.3	0.403	0.29
40	LLZO	garnet	100	1073	31.0	0.310	0.25
41	LLZO	garnet	80	1173	37.8	0.302	0.25
42	Al ₂ O ₃ :TZP	fluorite	100	1173	40.9	0.409	0.26
43	Al ₂ O ₃ :TZP	fluorite	100	1273	39.9	0.399	0.26
44	B ₄ C	carbide	350	1373	13.2	0.462	0.83
45	B ₄ C	carbide	200	1573	21.8	0.436	0.83
46	Doped-ZnO	wurtzite	100	773	33.0	0.330	0.26
47	Doped-ZnO	wurtzite	50	873	65.3	0.327	0.26
48	Doped-ZnO	wurtzite	30	973	108.5	0.326	0.26
49	Doped-TiO ₂	rutile	100	873	45.4	0.454	0.26
50	Doped-TiO ₂	rutile	50	973	89.0	0.445	0.26
51	Doped-TiO ₂	rutile	30	1073	145.2	0.436	0.26
52	α -Al ₂ O ₃	corundum	1500	1173	3.5	0.525	0.30
53	α -Al ₂ O ₃	corundum	750	1373	6.8	0.510	0.30
54	α -Al ₂ O ₃	corundum	750	1273	7.0	0.525	0.30
55	LLZO-RFS	garnet	100	973	31.9	0.319	0.25
56	LLZO-RFS	garnet	150	873	21.7	0.326	0.25
57	3YSZ	fluorite	150	1073	28.3	0.425	0.26
58	3YSZ	fluorite	200	1023	21.5	0.430	0.26
59	3YSZ	fluorite	150	1123	28.0	0.420	0.26
60	3YSZ	fluorite	200	1073	21.3	0.426	0.26
61	8YSZ	fluorite	150	973	29.1	0.437	0.26
62	8YSZ	fluorite	100	1073	42.5	0.425	0.26
63	8YSZ	fluorite	125	1023	34.4	0.430	0.26
64	WC	carbide	150	1073	184.2	2.763	0.83
65	WC	carbide	100	1173	269.9	2.699	0.83
66	WC	carbide	80	1273	329.2	2.634	0.83
67	WC	carbide	120	1123	227.6	2.731	0.83
68	WC	carbide	90	1223	296.2	2.666	0.83
69	HZO (thin film)	fluorite	2×10^9	-	0.01	2.000	-
70	Cu (intercon.)	FCC	14	623	10.0	0.014	-
71	Al (intercon.)	FCC	5.6	473	10.0	0.006	-
72	W (bulk wire)	BCC	0.011	-	86000	0.090	-
73	Pt (bulk wire)	FCC	0.007	-	69000	0.050	-

- [1] G. Ding, J. Duan, S. Cai, L. Dai, M. Jiang, E. Ma, F. Jiang, N. Xu, and B. Cui, Nat. Phys. **21**, 1911 (2025).
[2] M. Baggioli and A. Zaccane, Phys. Rev. Lett. **122**, 145501 (2019).

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